

Influence of Some Ionic and Non-Ionic Surfactants on the Electrode Reactions of Ga(III), In(III) and Ge(IV)

MAHESH CHANDRA DUBEY and MUKHTAR SINGH

Department of Chemistry, Arga College, Agra-282 002

Manuscript received 5 January 1980, revised 17 August 1981, accepted 7 January 1982

IN continuation of our earlier reports¹⁻³ on the influence of increasing concentrations of surfactants on the polarographic behaviour of Ni(II), Co(II), Zn(II), Mn(II) and UO₂(II), we now report our studies on the influence of increasing concentrations of some ionic and non-ionic surfactants, viz., lauryl pyridinium chloride (LPC), cetyl pyridinium chloride (CPC), cetyldimethyl benzyl ammonium chloride (CDBAC), sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS), dodecyl benzene sulphonate (DBS), dioctyl sodium sulphosuccinate (DSSS), ethyl digol, Triton X-100 and gelatin on the electrode reactions of Ga(III), In(III) and Ge(IV).

Experimental

Stock solutions of Ga(NO₃)₃·H₂O (Fluka, A.R.), GeO₂ (Fluka, A.R.) and In(NO₃)₃·3H₂O (E. Merck, G.R.) were prepared in conductivity water. The concentration of each of the depolarizers in the final solution to be polarographed was maintained at $1 \times 10^{-3} M$. All the surfactants were of high purity and used in their aqueous solutions. A manual polarograph (Toshniwal CL 02) in conjunction with a polyflex galvanometer (Toshniwal PL 50) was used. Purified nitrogen was used for removing dissolved oxygen. The potentials were measured against a saturated calomel electrode (S.C.E.). NaClO₄ (0.1 M) was used as a supporting electrolyte for Ga(III) and Ge(IV) while 0.1 M KCl was used for In(III). Observations were taken at a constant temperature, $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The d.m.e. had the following capillary characteristics (in 0.1 M NaClO₄, open circuit) $m = 1.89$ mg/sec; $t = 3.1$ sec; $m^{2/3} t^{1/3} = 1.84$ mg^{2/3} sec^{-1/3}; $h_{corr.} = 72.2$ cm.

The number of electrons (n) involved in the electroreduction of each of the depolarizers was determined by millicoulometric method⁴ and was found to be 3 for Ga(III) and In(III) and 4 for Ge(IV). Knowing the value of n , the diffusion coefficient (D) of the depolarizers was calculated by Ilkovic equation at different concentrations of the surfactants. The kinetic parameters (αn_a and $k_{f,n}^0$) were calculated by Koutecky's method^{5,6}. Throughout the measurements, the current at the end of the drop (i.e., the maximum current) was recorded, as according to Meites^{7,8} maximum current should be measured if the kinetic parameters for an irreversible wave are to be calculated by Koutecky's method.

Results and Discussion

In the absence of surfactants, both Ga(III) and Ge(IV) yield polarographic maxima under the

chosen experimental conditions but In(III) does not produce a maximum. The influence of increasing concentrations of ionic and non-ionic surfactants on the electrode reactions of Ga(III) and Ge(IV) has been studied beyond the stage where the maxima get just suppressed. The concentrations of the surfactants required for the just suppression of the maxima were for Ga(III): [LPC] = [CPC] = [CDBAC] = $1 \times 10^{-3}\%$, [SLS] = $4.0 \times 10^{-4}\%$, [DBS] = [DSSS] = $1.6 \times 10^{-3}\%$, [Triton X-100] = [gelatin] = $1.0 \times 10^{-3}\%$; for Ge(IV): [LPC] = [CPC] = $2.0 \times 10^{-4}\%$, [CDBAC] = $5.0 \times 10^{-4}\%$, [SLS] = [DBS] = [DSSS] = $2.0 \times 10^{-4}\%$, [ethyl digol] = 0.2% , [Triton X-100] = $1.0 \times 10^{-3}\%$. The wave-heights are diffusion-controlled in each case in the presence of increasing concentrations of the surfactants as shown by the linearity of i_d vs $h_{corr.}^{1/2}$ plots and their passing through the origin.

Irreversibility of the electrode reactions: The various tests of irreversibility⁷⁻⁹ indicate that the electrode reactions of Ga(III) and Ge(IV) are totally irreversible in the presence of increasing concentrations of ionic and non-ionic surfactants. However, the nature of the electrode reaction of In(III) is different. In 0.1 M KCl, In(III) gives a well-defined wave (without any maximum) whose slope (21.4 mV) corresponds closely to a reversible 3-electron reduction. This observation is supported by the reference given in the literature¹⁰. But on addition of increasing concentrations ($\geq 1 \times 10^{-3}\%$ in the case of anionic and non-ionic and $\geq 3 \times 10^{-3}\%$ in the case of cationic) of the surfactants the electrode reaction of In(III) becomes totally irreversible.

Influence of increasing concentrations of ionic and non-ionic surfactants on the kinetics of the electrode reactions of Ga(III), In(III) and Ge(IV):

(i) *Electrode reactions of Ga(III) and Ge(IV):* The values of kinetic parameters (αn_a and $k_{f,n}^0$) have been calculated as a function of the concentration of surfactants. The concentration variation was from $2 \times 10^{-4}\%$ to $8 \times 10^{-3}\%$. A perusal of these values shows that both αn_a and $k_{f,n}^0$ decrease as the concentration of the surfactant is gradually increased beyond the stage where the maxima get just suppressed. A decrease in the values of these parameters shows¹¹ that the irreversible electrode reactions of Ga(III) and Ge(IV) become more so on adding increasing amounts of ionic and non-ionic surfactants. This conclusion is supported by a decrease in i_d and a negative shift in $E_{1/2}$. These effects indicate inhibition¹² of the electrode processes of Ga(III) and Ge(IV) in the presence of increasing amounts of surfactants.

(ii) *Electrode reaction of In(III):* As already mentioned, the electrode reaction of In(III) in 0.1 M KCl and in the absence of a surfactant is reversible. But on the addition of cationic surfactants the electrode reaction tends towards irreversibility and becomes totally irreversible at [cationic surfactant] $\geq 3 \times 10^{-3}\%$. On the other hand the

addition of both anionic and non-ionic surfactants even at a lower concentration ($\geq 1 \times 10^{-3}\%$) renders the electrode reaction of In(III) totally irreversible. The values of αn_a and $k_{t,n}^0$ have been calculated at the concentrations of ionic and non-ionic surfactants where the electrode reaction of In(III) becomes totally irreversible and thereafter the influence of increasing concentrations of the surfactants on the values of the kinetic parameters has been studied. A perusal of these values shows that both αn_a and $k_{t,n}^0$ decrease with increasing concentrations of the surfactants. It follows from this that the reversible electrode reaction of In(III) in 0.1 M KCl tends towards irreversibility on the addition of ionic and non-ionic surfactants and that the electrode reaction becomes more irreversible with the addition of increasing concentrations of the surfactants. This is further supported by a decrease in i_d and a negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ in the presence of increasing concentrations of the surfactants. The decrease in i_d and a negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ with increasing concentrations of surfactants indicate^{1,2} inhibition of the electrode process of the depolarizers. This may be due to an increase in surface-coverage of the dropping mercury electrode^{1,4}.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. S. N. Srivastava, Principal, Agra College, Agra for interest in this work and for the facilities.

References

1. S. S. SHARMA, S. K. JHA and M. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, **15A**, 742.
2. M. C. DUBEY, R. RATAN, S. K. JHA and M. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, **16A**, 715.
3. M. C. DUBEY and M. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1979, **18A**, 174.
4. T. DEVIRES and J. L. KROON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 2484.
5. J. KOUTECKY, *Colln. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1953, **18**, 597.
6. J. KOUTECKY and J. CIZEK, *Colln. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1956, **21**, 836.
7. R. GOTO and I. TACHI, *Proc. Intern. Polarogr. Congr.*, 1951, **1**, 69.
8. P. RIVALO, K. B. OLDHAM and H. A. LAITINEN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 4148.
9. L. MEITES, "Polarographic Techniques", Interscience Publ., New York, 1965, p. 227.
10. I. M. KOLTHOFF and J. J. LINGANE, "Polarography", Interscience Publ., New York, 1952, Vol. 2, p. 519.
11. L. MEITES, "Polarographic Techniques", Interscience Publ., New York, 1965, p. 324.
12. J. HEYROVSKY and J. KUTA, "Principles of Polarography", Academic Press, New York, 1966, p. 299.
13. L. MEITES, "Polarographic Techniques", Interscience Publ., New York, 1965, p. 241.
14. M. M. ABOU ROMIA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1980, **19A**, 374.

Syntheses of 2-Hydroxyisocarbostyrils

J. N. CHATTERJEA, SANAT K. MUKHERJEE

and

C. BHAKTA

Department of Chemistry, Patna University, Patna-800 005

Manuscript received 16 September 1980, revised 29 June 1981,

accepted 7 January 1982

AS 2-hydroxyisocarbostyrils are effective anti-depressant and powerful tranquiliser¹, a convenient synthesis of this class of compounds is desirable. We reported² earlier the synthesis of 2-hydroxyisocarbostyrils by nitrosation of indan-1-ones and 3-alkyl(aryl)indan-1-ones with butyl nitrite in presence of sodium methoxide. Similar transformations of 2-alkylindan-1-ones have been described by Moriconi and coworkers^{3,4}. Earlier, indeno(3':2'-3:4)isocoumarin was converted into 2-hydroxyindeno(3':2'-3:4)isocarbostyril by the action of hydroxylamine⁵. We now report a synthesis of 2-hydroxyisocarbostyrils by the action of hydroxylamine hydrochloride on 4-acetylisochroman-1,3-dione, isocoumarins and isocoumarincarboxylic acids separately in the presence of pyridine.

2-Hydroxyisocarbostyrils (9 to 13) were obtained by heating isocoumarins (1 to 5), respectively, with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in presence of pyridine. Similar experiments on 3-methylisocoumarin-4-carboxylic acid (6) resulted in the formation of 2-hydroxy-3-methylisocoumarin (10) with decarboxylation, which was characterised by the preparation of its acetate and benzoate derivatives (Scheme 1). The pmr spectrum of 10 showed resonances at δ 2.58 (s, 3H, CH_3), 6.55 (broad s, 1H, vinyl), 8.5 (m, 3H, C-8 peri proton), 7.38-7.74 (m, 3H, aromatic) and 10.25 (broad, 1H, NOH exchangeable with D_2O). The ir spectrum of the same compound showed absorptions at 1640 cm^{-1} .

10 was also obtained from similar experiments on 4-acetylisochroman-1,3-dione (8). This transformation obviously involves a rearrangement and decarboxylation, which presumably follows the mechanistic course as in Scheme 2.

While this work was almost complete, we noticed a recent publication of Usgaonkar *et al*⁶ who reported similar conversion of 3-alkyl (Me, Et, Pr)-7-hydroxyisocoumarins and 3-alkyl (Me, Et, Pr)-7-hydroxyisocoumarin-4-carboxylic acids with hydroxylamine in presence of aqueous sodium carbonate. It is interesting to note that they obtained 3-alkyl(Me, Et, Pr)-2,7-dihydroxy-4-carboxyisocarbostyrils from the 4-acyl(MeCO, EtCO, PrCO)-7-hydroxyisochroman-1,3-diones while in our case we isolated the decarboxylated products from analogous experiments. The mechanism proposed by them (attack of hydroxylamine on acyl carbonyl group) does not seem to be tenable under the experimental conditions adopted by us.